

INVESTIGATION OF RESIDUAL STRESS STATES IN FIBRE REINFORCED CERAMIC COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The inevitably formed residual stresses derived from the manufacturing process of composite materials like carbon fibre reinforced silicon carbide matrix composites, are due to the different physical properties of the composite partners. These residual stresses are of interest because they represent an internal load which is superimposed by the external load in practical use. In a first step the influence of different process and structural parameters on the resulting residual stress state of pyrolytically produced samples were investigated by means of non-destructive X-ray diffraction method. Additionally the influence of the tensile residual stresses on the tensile strength of the composites is investigated.

1. INTRODUCTION

The reinforcement of a monolithic ceramic with endless fibres is a possibility to provide a damage tolerant failure of the composites retaining the positive properties of ceramics like high temperature strength, low density, low thermal expansion coefficient, good corrosion resistance, good heat conductivity and good abrasion resistance. Carbon fibre reinforced SiC-matrix composites are promising candidates for a lightweight structural material for high performance high temperature. For the fabrication of fibre reinforced ceramic composites different methods have been developed, e.g. infiltration and pyrolysis of SiC-powder filled polymers used by Dornier [1], liquid silicon infiltration by Deutsche Luft- und Raumfahrt (DLR) [2], CVI (chemical vapour infiltration) process by SEP (Société Européenne de Propulsion) and a modified CVI process working with temperature gradients to reduce the manufacturing time and cost by MAN [3]. During the fabrication of the composites residual stresses arise both in the fibre and matrix. In general they include terms associated with the difference of thermal expansion coefficients of fibre and matrix, as well as volume changes that occur upon crystallisation of the ceramic matrix. The residual stresses are important for the practical use of composites because they influence the strength and the damage tolerant failure behaviour of the composites. The internal stresses are superimposed by external loads, so tensile residual stress may limit the material strength. Additionally there is an important influence on the fracture mechanisms which determines the required damage-bearing stress-strain behaviour. The fracture properties of brittle matrix composites are governed by matrix cracking followed by interaction of these cracks with the fibres and interfaces (Figure 1). Within the composite the following micromechanisms are used as energy-dissipative processes:

debonding between fibre and matrix, crack bridging, fibre pull-out, multiple crack formation and crack deflection [4,5].

Figure 1: Schematic illustration showing the various contributions to the steady-state toughness by Evans [6]

Residual stresses parallel to the fibres influence the opening of matrix cracks and the debonding process, the prerequisite of a damage tolerant behaviour. The extent of debonding at the crack tip is typically small when residual compression exists at the interface, but can be extensive when the interface is in residual tension. Residual stresses normal to the fibre axis affect the frictional forces between fibre and matrix, so they have an important influence on the load transfer from fibre to matrix [7]. A small sliding resistance along the steady-state debonds thus promotes high "toughness". However, the sign and magnitude of the steady-state toughness change with residual stresses depending on mechanisms of interfacial sliding and fibre failure. The quantitative stress values depend on a large variety of processing and structural parameters. In order to investigate the formation of residual stresses near the surface region, X-ray diffraction measurements have been performed. These results will be connected to the mechanical properties of the samples.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 SAMPLES

The studies were performed on samples (C-fibre, SiC-matrix) delivered by Dornier, which were produced by impregnation and pyrolysis of polymers. The investigated samples exhibit a laminate structure. The orientation of the fibres within each layer is unidirectional and the layers are arranged alternately shifted around 90deg. The thickness of the layers is about 350 μ m. The surface roughness of the samples varies up to $\pm 20\mu$ m; additional microcracks are found across the whole surface in a distance of about some mm.

The investigated samples differ in the following processing as well as structural parameters:

1. Structural Parameters: fibre orientation, fibre volume, average fibre diameter, fibre/matrix, bonding (fibre coating)
2. Production Parameter: end temperatur of pyrolyses, pyrolyses time, preheating, annealing, reinfiltration

2.2 X-RAY DIFFRACTION

For X-ray diffraction investigations, Cu-K α radiation with a wavelength of $\lambda=0.15418\text{nm}$ was used. Depending on the diffraction angle 2θ and the sample inclination angle ψ relative to the incident beam a penetration depth of $50\ \mu\text{m}$ up to $80\ \mu\text{m}$ is achieved. Furthermore the divergency of the radiation was limited from 0.7deg up to $1.9\ \text{deg}$ by using circular collimators. The investigated samples contain pyrolytically produced crystalline SiC and SiC-powder, as a filler to reduce shrinkage during crystallisation of the ceramic matrix. For phase analysis the reflection pattern of the SiC powder and the sample (Figure 3) was registered in the range from 30deg to 150deg with a duration of 50s per degree.

Figure 2: Diffraction pattern of a C/SiC sample produced by pyrolysis of polymers

After subtraction of the SiC powder spectrum only SiC-peaks are present. The evaluation of the diffractograms show that the reflection of the ceramic matrix belong to the 6H polytype of the high temperature α -SiC, whereas the SiC-powder is of the 51R polytype [8]. In order to investigate the residual stresses in the SiC matrix it is advantageous to use a reflection at a high 2θ value as possible. Therefore SiC reflections were analyzed at $2\theta=109\text{deg}$ and $2\theta=120\text{deg}$, respectively. Hereby the reflection at $2\theta=109\text{deg}$ is a pure reflection from the SiC powdered filler whereas the reflection at $2\theta=120\text{deg}$ is a SiC powder filler reflection superimposed by pyrolytically produced crystalline SiC. For symmetry reasons no individual reflections of this phase are at disposal. Comparative measurements on both reflections did not exhibit significant differences so that eventual phase specific microstrains are within the experimental error bars. The measurement were carried out using a ψ -diffractometer using the ψ -mode predominantly. The interplanar lattice spacings d were measured in the ψ -range up to $\psi=\pm 63\text{deg}$ (ψ -inclination angle of the sample surface relative to the incident beam). A linear relationship of d versus $\sin^2\psi$ was observed and no significant d -splitting of the positive and negative ψ -branches could be detected. The calculation of the stress values was performed applying the $\sin^2\psi$ -law

[9]. The X-ray elastic constants (XEC) for the SiC-phase were taken from literature [10] and estimated to be $s_1 = -0.35 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{MPa}^{-1}$ and $1/2s_2 = 2.7 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{MPa}^{-1}$ for all lattice planes which were used for residual stress analysis. For the evaluation the XEC of the SiC-phase have been provisionally used since the analysis of the appropriated XEC is still in progress.

3. RESULTS

In the case of the pyrolytical samples with laminate structure the X-ray measurements yield stress values of the top laminate due to the penetration depth of $50\mu\text{m}$ up to $80\mu\text{m}$ in comparison to the laminate thickness of approximately $350\mu\text{m}$. Because of the anisotropic shrinkage of the matrix during the fabrication of the composite, the residual stresses will also arise between the different orientated laminates. The crossway shrinkage of the single laminate is restricted by the different orientations of the neighbour laminates. The resulting stresses will be relaxed by the development of translaminar cracks. This cracks separate each single laminate into segments, shown in figure 3. The anisotropic shrinkage of the matrix is superimposed by the anisotropic thermal expansion coefficient of the Carbon Fibre, which is positive perpendicular to the fibre axis and negative along the fibre axis [11].

Figure 3: Cutting perpendicular to the laminates in a 0/90deg orientated sample

3.1 RESIDUAL STRESS AS A FUNCTION OF PROCESSING PARAMETERS

In all samples tensile stresses are found parallel to the fibre orientation, whereas small and compressive stresses are present perpendicular to it. The tensile stress results from the superposition of a shrinkage of the matrix material during the pyrolytical process with the effects due to the thermal mismatch between fibres and matrix material. The existence of compressive stresses perpendicular to the fibre orientation indicates that the shrinkage is not significantly hindered in this direction.

The results of the residual stress analysis in samples with different end temperatures of the pyrolytical process measured in the SiC-matrix parallel to the fibres are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Development of residual stress as a function of the pyrolysis end temperature (content of pyrolytically produced SiC)

sample	end temperature of pyrolysis [°]	pyrolytically produced SiC [%]	residual stresses parallel to the fibres [MPa] (error: ± 14MPa)
1.3	1150	0	88
1.5	1300	39	230
1.6	1450	60	202
1.7	1600	100	284

Table 1 indicates that the increase in the end temperature of the pyrolytical process leads to an increase in the tensile matrix stresses. Additional investigations demonstrate, that the achieved stress level using different furnaces with the same end temperature depends on the grade of pyrolytical conversion and is less influenced by the absolute end temperature of the pyrolysis. Thus the matrix tensile stresses increase with increasing amount of pyrolytically produced SiC.

Table 2 shows that with increasing pyrolysis time the residual stress in the SiC-matrix passes through a maximum probably caused by energie dissipative mechanisms like microcracking, debonding, crack growth etc.

Table 2: Development of residual stress as a function of the pyrolysis time

sample	pyrolysis time [h]	residual stresses parallel to the fibres [MPa] (error: ± 20MPa)	residual stresses normal to the fibres [MPa]
6.1	16	220	-3 ± 4
6.2	22	360	-28 ± 10
6.3	33	150	-4.5 ± 2

Investigations of sample series with different preheating treatments and different annealing treatments show that tensile residual stresses may be relaxed significantly. The combination of preheating and annealing, however, is not favourable to the tensile stress state, since in this case, no further reduction is achieved. In some cases tensile stresses increase again. The most significant effect on the stress level is observed for samples with reinfiltration shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Development of residual stresses as a function of reinfiltration

sample	reinfiltration cycles	residual stresses parallel to the fibres [MPa] (error: ± 20MPa)	residual stresses normal to the fibres [MPa]
7.1	0	220	-3±2
7.2	2	500	-29±12
7.3	4	572	-63±20
7.4	6	552	-63±16

Table 3 shows the dependency of the residual stresses from the number of reinfiltration cycles. The residual stresses increase with the infiltration cycles and therefore with increasing density.

3.2 RESIDUAL STRESS AS A FUNCTION OF STRUCTURAL PARAMETERS

Typical results from measurements performed in the top laminate of two samples with different laminate orientations (0/90deg and 0/±45/90deg) are presented in Table 4. It is difficult to compare these results, because of the difference in the fibre volume fraction. Both the laminate orientation and the fibre volume fraction influence the development of the residual stress states within the sample. It seems that the different laminate orientations will influence the development of the compression residual stresses within one laminate. Whereas the influence of the fibre volume fraction is more important on the tensile residual stresses.

Table 4: Development of residual stresses as a function of the fibre volume fraction and the laminate orientation

sample	fibre orientation	fibre volume fraction	residual stress parallel to the fibres [MPa] (error ± 14MPa)	residual Stress normal to the fibres [MPa] (error ± 14MPa)
3.1	0/90	<	188	-82
3.2	0/±45/90	>	245	-55

A most important parameter for the properties of a composite is the fibre/matrix interface, so it is necessary to investigate the influence of a fibre coating on the residual stress state within the composite. The principal purpose of fibre coating is to modify the fracture behaviour by altering the mechanisms of bonding, stress states and thermo-mechanical properties at the fibre-matrix interface region which, in turn, determine the energy absorption capability of the composites. A weak fibre-matrix bond promotes interfacial debonding and subsequent frictional fibre pull-out, which gives rise to large contributions to the total composite fracture toughness. To achieve benefits of high transverse fracture toughness arising from these failure mechanisms, a coating layer has to provide a sufficiently high frictional bonding while maintaining a weak bonding at the interface. Thickness, internal subdivision, chemical composition and the particular microstructure of such a layer influence the properties of the composite [12,13]. First measurements show that a fibre coating influences the development of residual stresses within the composite. The tensile residual stresses parallel to the fibre axis decrease with a fibre coating. It is furthermore of interest to investigate different fibre coatings and their influence on the residual stresses, the composite failure behaviour and the development of the residual stresses under external load.

3.3 RESIDUAL STRESSES AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

The influence of matrix tensile stresses on the mechanical properties of the composites (tensile and shear strengths) were investigated. The results are summarized in Table 5 and Table 6.

Table 5: The influence of the tensile residual stresses on the tensile and shear strength of C/SiC samples pyrolysed at different end temperatures

sample	residual stresses parallel to the fibres [MPa] (error: ± 14MPa)	tensile strength [MPa]	shear strength [MPa]
1.3	157	126±19	6.6±0.3
1.5	230	32±8	5.9±1.1
1.6	202	86±9	5.2±0.3
1.7	284	77±2	5.1±0.3

Table 6: The influence of the tensile residual stresses on the tensile and shear strength of C/SiC samples with different reinfiltration cycles

sample	reinfiltration cycles	residual stresses parallel to the fibres [MPa] (error: ± 20 MPa)	tensile strength [MPa]	shear strength [MPa]
7.1	0	220	177	5.7
7.2	1	500	125	9.2
7.3	2	572	130	11.9
7.4	3	552	134	16.1

These data demonstrate that high tensile residual stresses reduce the tensile strength of the material and also, but less important, the shear strength. The samples with different reinfiltration cycles show an increase in the shear strength, because of the density increases with the reinfiltration.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

X-Ray diffraction investigations give information about the development of residual stresses in the matrix surface region of fibre reinforced ceramics. In the case of pyrolytical produced samples with 0/90deg orientated laminate structure remarkable tensile stresses were found parallel to the fibre orientation, whereas small and compressive stresses are present perpendicular to it. The tensile stresses result from the superposition of shrinkage of the matrix during the pyrolytical process with the effects due to the thermal mismatch between fibres and matrix material.

The most significant effect on the stress level was observed for samples with increasing infiltration cycles. Further this study shows the influence of the residual stresses on the strength of the composites and the failure behaviour. For the practical use the influence of the matrix tensile stresses on mechanical properties of the composites is very important, because high tensile residual stresses reduce the strength of the material. Investigations of the development of the tensile residual stresses under external load by means of in-situ X-ray diffraction measurements will be performed. In future the investigation of the fibrecoating, especially the type and thickness, is of major interesting. Furthermore it will be useful to investigate the residual stress state under influence of high temperatures and in the volume of the sample by using neutron diffraction.

5. REFERENCES

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